

ENHANCED MAP OUTAGE FACTOR OPTIMIZATION FOR WIMAX

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Abstract: *The emergence of WiMAX has attracted significant interests from all fields of wireless communications. WiMAX has been tipped to bring a revolution in the way where broadband services have been used today; those have been strengthened by the optimization of RF. The systematic investigation to establish facts of necessary modification about the theory for smooth optimization is targeted. This paper has considered factor attributes, mean sector throughput, mean subscriber SINR, system map outage, and map outage factor, and objective function for the invention of a method to produce suitable values which help to realize better output. Simulation results found to be more precise over conventional RF of WiMAX in finding the modification of the existing theory.*

Keywords: *WiMAX, RF, Object Function, Map Outage Factor, SINR.*

1. Introduction

RF signals are high frequency altering current signals composed of electromagnetic energy. RF signals are generated as electrical energy by the transmitting radio, passed along a copper wire along to the antenna and radiated into the air by the antenna. The antenna converts the wired signal to a wireless signal vice versa.

WiMAX is an IEEE 802.16 standard technology responsible for bringing the broadband wireless access to the world as an alternative to wired broadband. The WiMAX standard 802.16e provides fixed nomadic, portable and mobile wireless broadband connectivity without the need to direct line of signal with the base station. 802.16e adds the feature of mobility to the wireless broadband feature. There is some work on RF optimization in WiMAX [2-8]. Pazhyannur et al [2] have worked on Optimizer Requirements, Propagation Modeling, Mean system SINR, and Mean sector throughput, Propagation Algorithm. They developed a tool to

automate the process of “optimizing” system RF attributes. This system is currently in field testing. They also described the nature of the optimizer and the results obtained from laboratory testing. Y. H. Chen et al [3] introduced the architecture of the BFN controller and the steering operation modes of the BFN are also introduced. They analyzed the optimization of the antenna element spacing in considering of the mutual coupling against the grating lobe suppression. They also evaluated the performance

in measuring a tested Butler matrix array antenna by BFN. Ildu Kim et al [4] worked with the envelope signal of a Hybrid Envelope Elimination and Restoration (H-EER) technique. They improved linearity and efficiency, resulting in Envelope Tracking (ET) architecture. They also showed that the H-EER transmitter with ET shaping is the most suitable architecture for the highly linear and efficient Base

Transceiver Station transmitter. RF optimization in WiMAX system, the problem is in the map outage factor. The value of map outage factor is significant to optimize the RF in WiMAX. So, it is needed to get the desired value. To solve this problem, a new method has been introduced which gives the optimum values. Simulation and result have been tested and verified using Matlab. In this paper, an extended new formula and an algorithm have been proposed to optimize RF in WiMAX system and it is found to be more precise over conventional RF in finding the modification of the existing theory.

2. Backgrounds

WiMAX systems with a universal frequency reuse plan, doing so can cause severe outage owing to interference, particularly along the intercell and intersector edges. To mitigate this,

WiMAX allows for coordination of subchannel allocation to users at the cell edges such that there is minimal overlap. This allows for a more dynamic frequency allocation across sectors, based on loading and interference conditions, as opposed to traditional fixed frequency planning. Those users under good SINR conditions will have access to the full channel bandwidth and operate under a frequency reuse of 1. Those in poor SINR conditions will be allocated nonoverlapping subchannels such that they operate under a frequency reuse of 2, 3, or 4, depending on the number of nonoverlapping subchannel groups that are allocated to be shared among these users. This type of subchannel allocation leads to the effective reuse factor taking fractional values greater than 1. The variety of subchannelization schemes supported by WiMAX makes it possible to do this in a very flexible manner. Obviously, the downside is that cell edge users cannot have access to the full bandwidth of the channel, and hence their peak rates will be reduced. Although there must be many meaningful ways to combine the component measures of the objective function, the most obvious ways are as a weighted sum or "weighted" product wherein the weights are applied as exponents to the individual multiplicands. In either case, the weights serve to emphasize or deemphasize the individual component measures [1-8]. WiROS uses the product form. It is assumed the objective function F is to be minimized. The argument of the function F is an assignment S of physical attributes to the sector antennas of the system, the attributes of each antenna consisting of applied power, azimuth, electrical or mechanical downtilt, and height. For WiROS, the objective function takes the form:

$$F(S) = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_T(S)}\right)^\alpha \left(\frac{1}{\mu_S(S)}\right)^\beta (1 + \mu_M(S))^\gamma \dots (1)$$

where $\mu_T(S)$ = the mean sector throughput, $\mu_S(S)$ = the mean subscriber SINR, and $\mu_M(S)$ = the system map outage, all resulting from S, and where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \geq 0$ are inputs. In existing work, $\gamma = 3$ and $\alpha = 1, \beta = 0$ or $\alpha = 0, \beta = 1$ have been used with SINR [2]. Use of the map outage factor in the definition of F discourages the optimizer

from finding solutions which maximize the throughput or SINR of users in good coverage at the expense of putting disadvantaged users in outage. The form of the outage component deserves some discussions. Adding one to the map outage insures that the component is non-zero. This is important, because if any component becomes zero, optimization terminates prematurely. Also, setting $\gamma = 3$ roughly amplifies the effect of outage, as estimated by a Taylor expansion, by a factor of three.

3. Proposed Method, Simulations And Results

To optimize the RF of WiMAX systems, the existing theory [2] has option to improve the performance of factor. An algorithm and some features have been introduced to overcome the problem. In the existing theory, there is an objective function which measures the system performance. It is related with mean sector throughput, mean subscriber Signal Interference to Noise Ratio (SINR), system map outage (the percentage of subscribers whose SINR is too low to read map symbols). The objective function,

$$F(S) = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_T(S)}\right)^\alpha \left(\frac{1}{\mu_S(S)}\right)^\beta (1 + \mu_M(S))^\gamma \dots (2)$$

where $\mu_T(S)$ = the sector throughput,

$\mu_S(S)$ = mean subscriber SINR,

$\mu_M(S)$ = the system map outage,

Where $\alpha, \beta, \gamma \geq 0$ and $\alpha, \beta =$ factor attributes and $\gamma =$ map outage factor

In existing theory, they used $\gamma=3; \alpha=1; \beta=0$ or $\alpha=0; \beta=1$. If $\gamma=3$, then it discourages the optimizer from finding solution. If $\gamma=0$, then it is optimized perfectly. That's why this paper has proposed a formula with algorithm by which it gets some values ranges $0 \leq \gamma < 1$.

3.1 Formula

Here, the Gama, has been formed with additional parameters in eq.3

$$\text{Gama} = [a/b + a/c]^\alpha$$

$$\gamma = \left(\frac{a}{b} + \frac{a}{c}\right)^\alpha \dots (3)$$

Where,

$a=0-1$ (Increasing by 0.1) $\rightarrow$ Factor

Parameter 1

Serial	α	a	b	c	γ
1	1	0	0.3	1	0
2	1	0	0.4	0.1	0
3	1	0	0.4	0.2	0
4	1	0	0.4	0.3	0
5	1	0	0.4	0.4	0
6	1	0	0.4	0.5	0
7	1	0	0.4	0.6	0
8	1	0	0.4	0.7	0
9	1	0	0.4	0.8	0
10	1	0	0.4	0.9	0
11	1	0	0.4	1	0
12	1	0	0.5	0.1	0
13	1	0	0.5	0.2	0
14	1	0	0.5	0.3	0
15	1	0	0.5	0.4	0
16	1	0	0.5	0.5	0
17	1	0	0.5	0.6	0
18	1	0	0.5	0.7	0
19	1	0	0.5	0.8	0
20	1	0	0.5	0.9	0
21	1	0	0.5	1	0
22	1	0	0.6	0.1	0
23	1	0	0.6	0.2	0
24	1	0	0.6	0.3	0
25	1	0	0.6	0.4	0
26	1	0	0.6	0.5	0
27	1	0	0.6	0.6	0
28	1	0	0.6	0.7	0
29	1	0	0.6	0.8	0
30	1	0	0.6	0.9	0
31	1	0	0.6	1	0
32	1	0	0.7	0.1	0
33	1	0	0.7	0.2	0
34	1	0	0.7	0.3	0
35	1	0	0.7	0.4	0
36	1	0	0.7	0.5	0
37	1	0	0.7	0.6	0
38	1	0	0.7	0.7	0
39	1	0	0.7	0.8	0
40	1	0	0.7	0.9	0

b=0-1 (Increasing by 0.1) → Factor
Parameter 2

c=0-1 (Increasing by 0.1) → Factor
Parameter 3

alpha = 0 or 1

So the final proposed formula is in the following,

$$F(S) = \left(\frac{1}{\mu_T(S)}\right)^\alpha \left(\frac{1}{\mu_S(S)}\right)^\beta (1 + \mu_M(S))^{\left(\frac{a+a}{b+c}\right)^\alpha} \dots\dots\dots(4)$$

3.2 Algorithm of the program

Step 1: set the value of a,b,c, alpha & gama.

Step 2: Range of the value a,b,c [0 to 1],[where increasing .1], alpha =[0 or 1].

Step 3: gama =[a/b+a/c]^alpha.

Step 4:gama >=0 to ,gama <1.

Step 5:if gama>1, then it goes to step 2,if not, then program ends.

Step 6: Exit.

3.3 Data & Graph

Fig. 1 and Table represent graphically and tabular format for introducing the empirical data of α, a, b, c and γ which are extracted from the proposed method.

Figure 1 : Data in graphical representation for map outage factor

Table 1 Data represents in tabular form

Serial	α	a	b	c	Y
41	1	0	0.7	1	0
42	1	0	0.8	0.1	0
43	1	0	0.8	0.2	0
44	1	0	0.8	0.3	0
45	1	0	0.8	0.4	0
46	1	0	0.8	0.5	0
47	1	0	0.8	0.6	0
48	1	0	0.8	0.7	0
49	1	0	0.8	0.8	0
50	1	0	0.8	0.9	0
51	1	0	0.8	1	0
52	1	0	0.9	0.1	0
53	1	0	0.9	0.2	0
54	1	0	0.9	0.3	0
55	1	0	0.9	0.4	0
56	1	0	0.9	0.5	0
57	1	0	0.9	0.6	0
58	1	0	0.9	0.7	0
59	1	0	0.9	0.8	0
60	1	0	0.9	0.9	0
61	1	0	0.9	1	0
62	1	0	1	0.1	0
63	1	0	1	0.2	0
64	1	0	1	0.3	0
65	1	0	1	0.4	0
66	1	0	1	0.5	0
67	1	0	1	0.6	0
68	1	0	1	0.7	0
69	1	0	1	0.8	0
70	1	0	1	0.9	0
71	1	0	1	1	0
72	1	0.1	0.2	0.3	0.833333
73	1	0.1	0.2	0.4	0.75
74	1	0.1	0.2	0.5	0.7
75	1	0.1	0.2	0.6	0.666667
76	1	0.1	0.2	0.7	0.642857
77	1	0.1	0.2	0.8	0.625
78	1	0.1	0.2	0.9	0.611111
79	1	0.1	0.2	1	0.6
80					

Table 2 Data represents in tabular form

Serial	α	a	b	c	Y
81	1	0.1	0.2	1	0.6
82	1	0.1	0.3	0.2	0.833333
83	1	0.1	0.3	0.3	0.666667
84	1	0.1	0.3	0.4	0.583333
85	1	0.1	0.3	0.5	0.533333
86	1	0.1	0.3	0.6	0.5
87	1	0.1	0.3	0.7	0.47619
88	1	0.1	0.3	0.8	0.458333
89	1	0.1	0.3	0.9	0.444444
90	1	0.1	0.3	1	0.433333
91	1	0.1	0.4	0.2	0.75
92	1	0.1	0.4	0.3	0.583333
93	1	0.1	0.4	0.4	0.5
94	1	0.1	0.4	0.5	0.45
95	1	0.1	0.4	0.6	0.416667
96	1	0.1	0.4	0.7	0.392857
97	1	0.1	0.4	0.8	0.375
98	1	0.1	0.4	0.9	0.361111
99	1	0.1	0.4	1	0.35
100	1	0.1	0.5	0.2	0.7
101	1	0.1	0.5	0.3	0.533333
102	1	0.1	0.5	0.4	0.45
103	1	0.1	0.5	0.5	0.4
104	1	0.1	0.5	0.6	0.366667
105	1	0.1	0.5	0.7	0.342857
106	1	0.1	0.5	0.8	0.325
107	1	0.1	0.5	0.9	0.311111
108	1	0.1	0.5	1	0.3
109	1	0.1	0.6	0.2	0.666667
110	1	0.1	0.6	0.3	0.5
111	1	0.1	0.6	0.4	0.416667
112	1	0.1	0.6	0.5	0.366667
113	1	0.1	0.6	0.6	0.333333
114	1	0.1	0.6	0.7	0.309524
115	1	0.1	0.6	0.8	0.291667
116	1	0.1	0.6	0.9	0.277778
117	1	0.1	0.6	1	0.266667
118	1	0.1	0.7	0.2	0.642857
119	1	0.1	0.7	0.3	0.47619

Table 3 Data represents in tabular form

Serial	α	a	b	c	γ
160	1	0.1	0.7	0.4	0.392857
161	1	0.1	0.7	0.5	0.342857
162	1	0.1	0.7	0.6	0.309524
163	1	0.1	0.7	0.7	0.285714
164	1	0.1	0.7	0.8	0.267857
165	1	0.1	0.7	0.9	0.253968
166	1	0.1	0.8	1	0.225
167	1	0.1	0.8	0.2	0.625
168	1	0.1	0.8	0.3	0.458333
169	1	0.1	0.8	0.4	0.375
170	1	0.1	0.8	0.5	0.325
171	1	0.1	0.8	0.6	0.291667
172	1	0.1	0.8	0.7	0.267857
173	1	0.1	0.8	0.8	0.25
174	1	0.1	0.8	0.9	0.236111
175	1	0.1	0.8	1	0.225
176	1	0.1	0.9	0.2	0.611111
177	1	0.1	0.9	0.3	0.444444
178	1	0.1	0.9	0.4	0.361111
179	1	0.1	0.9	0.5	0.311111
180	1	0.1	0.9	0.6	0.277778
181	1	0.1	0.9	0.7	0.253968
182	1	0.1	0.9	0.8	0.236111
183	1	0.1	0.9	0.9	0.222222
184	1	0.1	0.9	1	0.211111
185	1	0.1	1	0.2	0.6
186	1	0.1	1	0.3	0.433333
187	1	0.1	1	0.4	0.35
188	1	0.1	1	0.5	0.3
189	1	0.1	1	0.6	0.266667
190	1	0.1	1	0.7	0.242857
191	1	0.1	1	0.8	0.225
192	1	0.1	1	0.9	0.211111
193	1	0.1	1	1	0.2
194	1	0.2	0.3	0.7	0.952381
195	1	0.2	0.3	0.8	0.916667
196	1	0.2	0.3	0.9	0.888889
197	1	0.2	0.3	1	0.866667
198	1	0.2	0.4	0.5	0.9

Table 4 Data represents in tabular form

Serial	α	a	b	c	γ
120	1	0.2	0.4	6	0.533333
121	1	0.2	0.4	0.7	0.785714
122	1	0.2	0.4	0.8	0.75
123	1	0.2	0.4	0.9	0.722222
124	1	0.2	0.4	1	0.7
125	1	0.2	0.5	0.4	0.9
126	1	0.2	0.5	0.5	0.8
127	1	0.2	0.5	0.6	0.733333
128	1	0.2	0.5	0.7	0.685714
129	1	0.2	0.5	0.8	0.65
130	1	0.2	0.5	0.9	0.622222
131	1	0.2	0.5	1	0.6
132	1	0.2	0.6	0.4	0.833333
133	1	0.2	0.6	0.5	0.733333
134	1	0.2	0.6	0.6	0.666667
135	1	0.2	0.6	0.7	0.619048
136	1	0.2	0.6	0.8	0.583333
137	1	0.2	0.6	0.9	0.555556
138	1	0.2	0.6	1	0.533333
139	1	0.2	0.7	0.3	0.952381
140	1	0.2	0.7	0.4	0.785714
141	1	0.2	0.7	0.5	0.685714
142	1	0.2	0.7	0.6	0.619048
143	1	0.2	0.7	0.7	0.571429
144	1	0.2	0.7	0.8	0.535714
145	1	0.2	0.7	0.9	0.507937
146	1	0.2	0.7	1	0.485714
147	1	0.2	0.8	0.3	0.916667
148	1	0.2	0.8	0.4	0.75
149	1	0.2	0.8	0.5	0.65
150	1	0.2	0.8	0.6	0.583333
151	1	0.2	0.8	0.7	0.535714
152	1	0.2	0.8	0.8	0.5
153	1	0.2	0.8	0.9	0.472222
154	1	0.2	0.8	1	0.45
155	1	0.2	0.9	0.3	0.888889
156	1	0.2	0.9	0.4	0.722222
157	1	0.2	0.9	0.5	0.622222
158	1	0.2	0.9	0.6	0.555556
159	1	0.2	0.9	0.7	0.507937

Table 5 Data represents in tabular form

Serial	α	a	b	c	γ
199	1	0.2	0.9	0.8	0.472222
200	1	0.2	0.9	0.9	0.444444
201	1	0.2	0.9	1	0.422222
202	1	0.2	1	0.3	0.866667
203	1	0.2	1	0.4	0.7
204	1	0.2	1	0.5	0.6
205	1	0.2	1	0.6	0.533333
206	1	0.2	1	0.7	0.485714
207	1	0.2	1	0.8	0.45
208	1	0.2	1	0.9	0.422222
209	1	0.2	1	1	0.4
210	1	0.3	0.5	0.8	0.975
211	1	0.3	0.5	0.9	0.933333
212	1	0.3	0.5	1	0.9
213	1	0.3	0.6	0.7	0.928571
214	1	0.3	0.6	0.8	0.875
215	1	0.3	0.6	0.9	0.833333
216	1	0.3	0.6	1	0.8
217	1	0.3	0.7	0.6	0.928571
218	1	0.3	0.7	0.7	0.857143
219	1	0.3	0.7	0.8	0.803571
220	1	0.3	0.7	0.9	0.761905
221	1	0.3	0.7	1	0.728571
222	1	0.3	0.8	0.5	0.975
223	1	0.3	0.8	0.6	0.875
224	1	0.3	0.8	0.7	0.803571
225	1	0.3	0.8	0.8	0.75
226	1	0.3	0.8	0.9	0.708333
227	1	0.3	0.8	1	0.675
228	1	0.3	0.9	0.5	0.933333
229	1	0.3	0.9	0.6	0.833333
230	1	0.3	0.9	0.7	0.761905
231	1	0.3	0.9	0.8	0.708333
232	1	0.3	0.9	0.9	0.666667
233	1	0.3	0.9	1	0.633333
234	1	0.3	1	0.5	0.9
235	1	0.3	1	0.6	0.8
236	1	0.3	1	0.7	0.728571
237	1	0.3	1	0.8	0.675
238	1	0.3	1	0.9	0.633333

In this work, a formula has been introduced of map outage factor. In this formula, it appears the value of map outage factor which ranges from 0 to 1. There are 237 values of map outage factor. The paper which has been developed [2], there map outage factor is 3, discards the objective function for better optimization. For that reason, RF does not work smoothly in WiMAX system. In this paper, the value of map outage factor, which is less than 3, has been found and it is effective and it works significantly.

In later section the value of the objective Function has also been optimized in terms of map outage factor's parameters. In existing work, it is mentioned that it is better to minimize the value of objective function, but they don't verify it. It has been completed to minimize the value of that given function. The value of mean sector throughput is 5.2 Mbps in the conventional system [2]. They did not provide any value of system map outage and mean subscriber SINR. But in order to calculate the value of the given function, this value is needed. That's why it is assumed the value of system map outage and mean subscriber SINR. Both of these values are 2 to calculate the values of function are assumed. Already 237 different values of gamma (γ = map outage factor) have been obtained using the proposed formula and algorithm. The value of F with different values of gamma has also been analyzed. There are 2 factor attributes: one is alpha (α) and another is beta (β). In first case, alpha is 1 and beta is 0 are considered. If the value of gamma is 3, then the value of F is 5.192. When the value of gamma is set, then some value of objective function which is less than 5.192 are appeared. 20 different values of gamma have been tested randomly. The tabular and graphical representations of the obtained data are shown in fig. 2, table IV, fig.3, and table V respectively.

Figure 2 : Data of objective function in graphical representation (Alpha 1, Beta 0)

Table 6 Data representation of objective function

mean Sector throughput	mean subscriber sinr	system map outage	alpha	beta	gama	function
5.2	2	2	1	0	3	5.192
5.2	2	2	1	0	0	0.192
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.83333	0.48
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.7	0.4149
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.625	0.382
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.6	0.371
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.6111	0.376
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.5333	0.345
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.4719	0.322
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.3918	0.296
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.3428	0.28
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.253968	0.254
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.291667	0.264
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.3	0.267
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.2	0.239
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.9	0.516
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.75	0.438
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.8	0.463
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.5556	0.354
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.952381	0.547
5.2	2	2	1	0	0.708333	0.418

After that it is also tested another case, where alpha (α) is 0 and beta (β) is 1. In that case when the value of gamma ($\gamma =$ map outage factor) is 3, the value of F is 13.5. When the value of gamma is set, then the acquired values are taken which are less than 13.5. 20 different values of gamma have also been tested here randomly. These are the graph and data

Figure 3 : Data of objective function in graphical representation (Alpha 0, Beta 1)

Table 7 Data representation of objective function

mean Sector throughput	mean subscriber sinr	system map outage	alpha	beta	gama	function2
5.2	2	2	0	1	3	13.5
5.2	2	2	0	1	3	13.5
5.2	2	2	0	1	0	0.5
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.8333	1.249
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.7	0.788
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.625	0.993
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.6	0.966
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.6111	0.978
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.5333	0.898
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.4719	0.839
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.3918	0.769
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.3428	0.728
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.253968	0.66
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.291667	0.688
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.3	0.695
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.2	0.622
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.9	1.34
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.75	1.139
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.8	1.204
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.5556	0.737
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.952381	1.423
5.2	2	2	0	1	0.708333	1.088

In conventional method, it is clarified that they could alternate the value of alpha and beta. But in proposed method, it has been suggested that if alpha is 1 and beta is 0, the value of optimization function is smaller than alpha is 0 and beta is 1. But in that case mean subscriber SINR and system map outage must be smaller than mean sector throughput.

4. Conclusions

In this paper, an enhanced RF optimization of WiMAX has been analyzed by a simplified formula of map outage factor which works with immense perfection. Comparing with the existing method, it is found that the proposed simplified formula works more precisely to minimize the objective function. To verify the result, the performance of the proposed system

has been examined by MATLAB simulator and it is established that the proposed modified formula is better than the existing technique to optimize RF of WiMAX.

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